

Thermodynamics of Ferrous-1,10-Phenanthroline in *t*-Butanol-Water and Glycerol-Water Media at 25°

A. K. MANDAL, S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. ADITYA

Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

The enthalpies of formation of ferrous-1,10-phenanthroline in *t*-BuOH-water and glycerol-water mixtures at 25° have been determined by calorimetry. The stability constants of the complex in the above mixed solvents have been determined spectrophotometrically. The entropy-changes have been evaluated combining the enthalpy values with the corresponding free energy changes calculated from *pK* values. The role of solvents on the thermodynamic parameters has been discussed.

1,10-Phenanthroline and its Fe(II) complex are well known for their use in analytical chemistry and also in view of their possible use as corrosion-inhibitors in boilers¹. Since the first determination of the stability constants of phenanthroline ion and its ferrous complex by Dwyer and Nyholm², different workers³⁻¹¹ have studied these systems. Lahiri and Aditya¹² made a detailed spectrophotometric study and reported on the thermodynamic properties of phenanthroline ion, ferriin and ferriin in aqueous medium. The dissociation constants as well as the enthalpies of the reactions in methanol-water medium were studied in this laboratory by Biswas and Aditya¹³. We also presented in an earlier communication¹⁴ the thermodynamics of 2,2'-dipyridinium ion and 1,10-phenanthroline ion in *t*-butanol-water and glycerol-water media at 25°. In this communication we report the enthalpies of formation of FePh₃²⁺ in different *t*-butanol- and glycerol-water mixtures at 25° determined by calorimetry and the dissociation constants by spectrophotometry. ΔG° and ΔS° values were calculated from these experimental results.

Experimental

The solutions were prepared as reported earlier^{14,15}. Purification of solvents was described in an earlier communication¹⁶.

For the measurement of enthalpy change we used a microcalorimeter fabricated in this laboratory^{17,18}. Experimental determinations were carried out in the same way as described in the case of Fedipy₂²⁺ reported earlier¹⁵. In the present case also we note that the addition of a small volume of Mohr solution to a large excess of 1,10-phenanthroline gives a constant value of ΔH in the *pH*-range used. The heat change due to the formation of PhH⁺ ion was taken into account. For the purpose, blank experiment with no Mohr salt (5 ml of solution containing HClO₄ and 250 ml of Ph) was done. The concentration of Ph was always more than 30 times the concentration of Fe²⁺ ion. The stability constants of FePh₃²⁺ were determined in *t*-butanol- and glycerol-water mixtures spectrophotometrically

at 25° with a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer as reported in detail earlier¹⁹.

Results and Discussion

From the measured heat liberated, enthalpy change per mole for the reaction $\text{Fe}^{2+} + 3 \text{Ph} \rightleftharpoons \text{FePh}_3^{2+}$ was calculated, using the relation $\Delta H = -\frac{Q}{x}$, where *Q* represents the heat liberated in Joules for *x* moles of FePh₃²⁺ formed. The reaction is iso-electric and as such ionic strength has very little effect. So the experimentally determined ΔH s have been taken as ΔH° s. The dissociation constants and the ΔH° s for FePh₃²⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ Fe²⁺ + 3Ph, in *t*-butanol- and glycerol-water have been presented in columns 2 and 3 of Table 2 and in columns 6 and 7 of Table 3, respectively.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMICS OF FePh₃²⁺ IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 25°

Reaction	ΔG° (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔS° (kJ mole ⁻¹)
FePh ₃ ²⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ Fe ²⁺ + 3Ph	116.90	131.04 ^a	47.28
	119.24	138.07 ^b	64.43
	117.70	129.70 ^c	40.27

a = Spectrophotometric value¹¹.

b = Calorimetric value¹⁹.

c = Our values extrapolated from lower percentages of organic solvent.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMICS OF FePh₃²⁺ $\rightleftharpoons$ Fe²⁺ + 3Ph IN *t*-BUTANOL AND GLYCEROL-WATER MEDIA AT 25°

Wt % of solvent	<i>pK</i> values	
	Glycerol-water	<i>t</i> -butanol-water
0	20.70 (± 0.48) ^a	20.70 (± 0.48)
10	20.52	20.20
20	20.66	19.70
30	19.70	19.10
40	19.92 (± 1.10)	17.50
50	—	17.00 (± 0.81)

^a Values in parentheses indicate maximum errors.

The thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ for the above reaction in *t*-butanol- and glycerol-water have been compiled in columns

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMICS OF $\text{FePh}_3^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{2+} + 3\text{Ph}$ IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT MEDIA AT 25°

Wt % of solvent	ΔG° (kJ mole ⁻¹)				ΔH° (kJ mole ⁻¹)				$T\Delta S^\circ$ (kJ mole ⁻¹)			
	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH	Glycerol	<i>t</i> -BuOH	EtOH	MeOH
0	117.70	117.70	117.12	116.90	129.70	129.70	129.91	131.40	12.00	12.00	12.79	14.14
10	116.65	114.85	113.00	114.22	136.10	137.48	130.87	148.53	19.45	22.63	17.87	34.31
20	117.44	112.01	109.00	111.71	149.07	153.22	133.22	166.94	31.63	41.21	24.22	55.23
30	112.00	108.57	104.90	109.20	145.73	172.13	128.45	167.78	33.73	63.56	23.55	58.58
40	113.35	99.50	100.05	106.69	142.42	156.32	—	156.90	29.07	56.82	—	50.21
50	—	96.65	96.50	104.18	139.95	150.58	—	148.11	—	53.93	—	43.93

Values of ΔG° at 15% and 25% for glycerol-water media are 116.10 and 114.60 kJ mole⁻¹, and for *t*-BuOH-water media are 117.90 and 109.20 kJ mole⁻¹, respectively.

Values ΔH° at 2.5% and 5% for glycerol-water media are 131.00 (± 0.02) and 132.67 (± 0.04) kJ mole⁻¹ and for *t*-BuOH-water media are 131.54 (± 0.03) and 133.51 (± 0.04) kJ mole⁻¹, respectively.

2, 3, 6, 7, 10, 11 of Table 3 along with the same in EtOH^{17,20} and MeOH-water¹⁸ (reported earlier) in columns 4, 5, 8, 9, 12, 13 of the same table. The Figs. 1, 2 and 3 indicate the nature of the plots of ΔH° , ΔG° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ against wt %, mole-fraction of organic solvent and reciprocal of the dielectric constant of aqueo-organic solvents, respectively. The dielectric constant values necessary are taken from Conway²¹ and Akerlof²². We have also determined the same parameters in water from the extrapolation of the ΔH° and ΔG° values in the region of lower percentages of organic components in water. The values of the thermodynamic parameters of FePh_3^{2+} in water in literature along with ours are presented in Table 1. The present values are in good agreement with those of Anderegg¹¹ and Lahiri and Aditya²³.

In the Figs. 1 and 2 it is seen that ΔG° changes linearly upto 30% of *t*-BuOH (which corresponds to

Fig. 1. Plot of ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ vs wt % of organic component.

Fig. 2. Plot of ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ vs mole fraction of organic component.

a mole-fraction of 0.09) and 20% of glycerol (corresponding to a mole-fraction of 0.04) and deviates at higher percentages. The variation of ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ values with solvent composition is not linear. The values at first increase with increasing organic solvent and pass through a maximum at about 30% in case of *t*-BuOH and 20% in case of glycerol in the respective solvent mixtures. Similar behaviour has been observed by us in case of PhH^+ in *t*-BuOH- and glycerol-water mixtures¹⁴ and also in case of dipyH^+ and Fe(II)-dipy complexes¹⁵. Such type of maximum structuration was also supported by Mishchenko *et al*²⁴, Krestov and Klopov²⁴, Pointud *et al*²⁵.

The interpretation of the thermodynamic data in mixed solvents is extremely difficult as it involves a knowledge of the structure of the liquid mixture and structure modification of the media when an ionic

Fig. 3. Plot of ΔG° , ΔH° and $T\Delta S^\circ$ vs $1/D$ of solvent mixture (D = dielectric constant).

system is introduced in the media, in addition to ionic solvation effects.

The free energy change of transfer, ΔG°_f , which consists of electric and non-electric contributions [$\Delta G^\circ_f = \Delta G^\circ_{f(e)} + \Delta G^\circ_{f(non-e)}$], in the present case will be mainly due to ion solvent and solvent-solvent interactions (non-electric part). Since the reaction is iso-electric, $\Delta G^\circ_{f(e)}$ will be negligible due to the small difference in the ionic ratio of $FePh_3^{2+}$ and $Fe(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ which is always solvated. ΔG°_f indicates that the reaction is favoured in mixed solvents. This is possibly because of (i) higher solubility of 'Ph' in the mixed solvents, (ii) the difference in the solvational properties of $Fe(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ and $FePh_3^{2+}$ in the media, and (iii) the solvent-solvent interaction.

The entropy change of transfer of different ionic species participating in the reaction will depend on difference in entropy of the solvent media. As discussed in our earlier communication¹⁶ for $Fe(dipy)_3^{2+}$, we have for the entropy change of $FePh_3^{2+}$

$$T\Delta S^\circ_f = T\Delta S_{f(Fe^{2+})} + 3T\Delta S_{f(Ph)} - T\Delta S_{f(FePh_3^{2+})}$$

The value of $T\Delta S^\circ_f$ passes through a maximum based on the models by Franks and Reid²⁶, Kundu et al²⁷ and other workers²⁸⁻³⁰.

The variation of ΔH° with solvent composition in case of $Fe(Ph)_3^{2+}$ is found to be similar to that observed in case of $Fe(dipy)_3^{2+}$. The models have been discussed in details^{14,15}. (The thermodynamic parameters for $Fe(II)$ -1,10-phenanthroline complex in general vary with composition of the solvent in the same manner as the $Fe(II)$ -dipy complex.

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